

INVITATION LETTER

Dear [Participant],

My name is Mariam El Mezouar. I am a PhD student at Queen's University, Canada supervised by Dr. Ying Zou (ying.zou@queensu.ca). I am inviting you to participate in a survey about developers' chatroom because you are an active GitHub contributor. We apologize in advance if our email is unwanted or a waste of your time.

This study will help us understand how tools like Gitter or Slack support the software development process. There are no mandatory questions in our survey and it will likely take only 15 mins of your time. To participate, please click on this link <https://goo.gl/forms/oX4UqWUDRcykBP372>.

Please note that it is possible to withdraw your survey submission within 3 weeks, by simply emailing the researchers. The data collected from the survey will be securely stored on a single computer machine at the research lab of the researchers within Queen's university.

To compensate you for your time, you may win a \$10 Amazon gift card if you complete the full questionnaire. We are offering these gift cards to 30% randomly drawn participants who complete the questionnaire. We would also be happy to share with you a summary of the survey results by email, if you are interested.

If you have any questions about this survey, or difficulty in accessing the site or completing the survey, please contact Mariam El Mezouar at mariam.el.mezouar@queensu.ca or Daniel Alencar da Costa at daniel.alencar@queensu.ca. Thank you in advance for your time and for providing this important feedback!

Any ethical concerns about the study may be directed to the Chair of the General Research Ethics Board at chair.GREB@queensu.ca or 1-844-535-2988 (Toll free in North America).

DISCLAIMER: We have no affiliation with any business or commercial entities. This is a one time request for your participation in an academic survey. You will not receive any further unsolicited emails from us.

Best Regards,

Mariam El Mezouar

PhD Candidate

Queen's University